

Histidine based fluorescence probe for nanomolar magnesium(II)

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Abstract : A magnesium selective turn-on fluorescence probe, HISDAL is prepared by condensing 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol with L-histidine methyl ester hydrochloride. HISDAL can detect as low as 5.0×10^{-9} mol L⁻¹ Mg²⁺ with a very short response time (< 1 s) without any interference from common ions, especially Ca²⁺.

Keywords : Magnesium, fluorescence, histidine, nanomolar.

Introduction

Magnesium is the second most abundant intracellular cation (K > Mg) and fourth most abundant cation in terms of total body mass of mammals including humans (Ca > K > Na > Mg)¹. Relatively low ionic radius in proportion to the size of the nucleus (0.86 vs. 1.14 Å for Ca, the most abundant cation in the human body) is responsible for its stability and exceptional activity in biological systems. It is a cofactor in more than 300 enzymes, controlling different biochemical reactions². It participates in several metabolic processes, including transformation of proteins, lipids, carbohydrates and nucleic acids as well as electrolyte transport across cell membranes. It regulates the proper electric potential of neurons, cell proliferation, ion channel regulation, stabilization of DNA conformation, glucose metabolism, maintenance of cell shape and signal transduction³. It is also necessary for the proper functioning of most of the ATPases and involved in insulin secretion, binding and activity⁴. Alteration of the intracellular and extracellular total or free content of magnesium from the mM range provokes many relevant pathological and symptomatic alterations in the human organism including migraine headaches, tachycardia (rapid heartbeat) and other cardiovascular diseases, cerebral infarction, osteoporosis, diabetes mellitus (DM), lung cancer, muscle dysfunction, sickle cell disease and hallucination⁵⁻¹⁰.

In spite of these important biological functions, in contrast to numerous Ca²⁺ fluorescent probes, there are only a few examples of promising Mg²⁺ fluorescent probes¹¹, which are mainly based on a charged β -diketone¹², calix[4]arene¹³, crown ether¹⁴, 1-naphthalene-acetamide¹⁵, polyether¹⁶ and 8-hydroxyquinoline¹⁷. However, Schiff base probes, easily prepared by the condensation of aldehydes and amines, stabilize different cations *via* coordination, have been considered to be the most "privileged" one¹⁸. Discrimination between Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ for most of the reported Mg²⁺ sensors are also unsatisfactory¹⁹. Hence, selective Mg²⁺ detection is a major concern in the areas of biochemical, environmental and medical sciences.

Herein, we report facile synthesis and photo physical properties of HISDAL, prepared by condensing 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol with histidine, and its selective and real-time (<1 s) determination of Mg²⁺ at physiological pH. Other common metal ions, especially Ca²⁺ do not interfere.

Results and discussion

The optimization of pH suggests that pH 6–11 is useful for fluorescence measurements (Fig. 1) and hence, all measurements have been performed in 0.1 M HEPES buffered aqueous-methanol (1 : 9, v : v) solution at pH 7.4, the physiological pH.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of HISDAL.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the emission intensity of free HISDAL (30 μM) and [HISDAL + Mg^{2+}] system (1 : 10, mole ratio, λ_{ex} , 365 nm; λ_{em} , 465 nm).

The fluorescence spectrum of HISDAL (30 μM , λ_{ex} , 365 nm, Fig. 2) shows weak emission intensity at 465 nm with a quantum yield (Φ_{HISDAL}), 1.19×10^{-2} . Upon addition of Mg^{2+} , emission intensity enhances 6.4 times while the fluorescence quantum yield ($\Phi_{\text{HISDAL}+\text{Mg}^{2+}}$) enhances 8.8 times to 10.54×10^{-2} . Plot of emission intensity of HISDAL as a function of Mg^{2+} concentration (Fig. 8) is linear up to 10 μM Mg^{2+} (Fig. 9), useful for unknown Mg^{2+} determination. The fluorescence enhancement is attributed to the combined effect of inhibition of ICT due to chelation with Mg^{2+} , named as chelation enhanced fluorescence (CHEF). Chelation also increases the rigidity of the molecular assembly by

Fig. 2. Changes in the emission intensity of HISDAL (30 μM , aqueous-methanol, 1 : 9, v/v) upon gradual addition of Mg^{2+} (0–300 μM), (λ_{ex} , 365 nm; λ_{em} , 465 nm).

restricting the free rotation around the azomethine functionality (Fig. 3). The UV-Vis absorption spectrum of HISDAL contains two bands at 210 and 290 nm, both of which increase with the serial addition of Mg^{2+} (Fig. 10).

HISDAL can detect as low as 5.0×10^{-9} mol L^{-1} Mg^{2+} , below the level in living cells, allowing determination of intracellular Mg^{2+} .

The effect of common metal ions on the emission intensity of the [HISDAL + Mg^{2+}] system (Fig. 11) shows no significant interference. Further, the selectivity of

Fig. 3. Proposed Mg^{2+} sensing mechanism.

Fig. 4. Selectivity of HISDAL (30 μ M) for Mg^{2+} in aqueous-methanol (1 : 9, v/v, λ_{ex} , 365 nm, λ_{em} , 465 nm).

HISDAL towards Mg^{2+} is established by recording the fluorescence spectra of HISDAL in presence of individual common cations (Fig. 4). Color of HISDAL in presence of various cations under UV light is shown in Fig. 12.

The Job's plot (Fig. 13) indicates a 1 : 1 binding interaction of HISDAL with Mg^{2+} , also supported by the mass spectra of the [HISDAL + Mg^{2+}] adduct (Fig. 14). Modified Benesi-Hildebrand method generates an association constant, $8.78 \times 10^4 M^{-1}$ for Mg^{2+} , indicating a significant strong interaction between HISDAL and Mg^{2+} (Fig. 15). The FTIR spectra of free HISDAL and its Mg^{2+} adduct are shown in Fig. 16.

Conclusion

In summary, we have designed a very simple real-time fluorescence probe HISDAL that can selectively monitor nanomolar Mg^{2+} through chelation enhanced fluorescence mechanism.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals are reagent grade while solvents are spectroscopy grade and used without further purification. Milli-Q $18.2 M\Omega\ cm^{-1}$ water is used in all experiments. $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ is used as the source of Mg^{2+} while the sources of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cr^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} ions are either their chloride, nitrate or perchlorate salts.

Synthesis of HISDAL :

2,6-Diformyl-4-methylphenol is synthesized starting from *p*-cresol following a published procedure²⁰. The probe, HISDAL has been synthesized by refluxing methanol solution of 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol and L-histidine methyl ester hydrochloride (1 : 2, mole ratio) in presence of sodium bicarbonate (Scheme 1) followed by solvent extraction of the crude product (obtained by removal of solvent using rotary evaporator) with ethyl acetate-water system. The slow evaporation of the organic solvent yields a brown solid, the molecular structure and purity of which are ensured from different spectroscopic studies like 1H NMR (600 MHz, $DMSO-d_6$), Fig. 5 shows that the 'd' protons of the heterocyclic rings of the histidine moiety come resonance at two different positions δ 7.50 and 7.61, this is probable due to the rotation of the rings through the C-C single bonds and interaction of the 'd' protons with 'g' and 'b' protons electron clouds; ESI-TOF-MS (Fig. 6) : $[M+H]^+ = 467.31$, $[M+Na]^+ =$

Fig. 5. ¹H NMR spectrum of HISDAL in DMSO-*d*₆.

Fig. 6. QTOF-MS spectrum of HISDAL in CH₃OH.

489.28 and FTIR (Fig. 7). The FTIR (cm^{-1}) spectrum of HISDAL contains bands at $\nu(\text{C-O})$, 1039; $\nu(\text{C=N})$, 1595; $\nu(\text{C=O})$ 1625.

Synthesis of [HISDAL + Mg^{2+}] complex :

To methanol solution of HISDAL (50 mg, 0.1072

mmol), 2 mL solution of MgSO_4 (25 mg, 0.1014 mmol) in water is added drop-wise and stirred for 10 min. The solution is kept for evaporation of the solvent to get a chocolate-brown colored compound. QTOF-MS ES^+ (Fig. 14) : corresponding to $[\text{HISDAL} + \text{Mg}^{2+} + 2\text{CH}_3\text{OH}]^+ = 554.68$; FTIR/ cm^{-1} (Fig. 16), $\nu(\text{C-O})$, 1058; $\nu(\text{C=N})$,

Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of HISDAL.

Fig. 8. Plot of emission intensities of HISDAL (30 μM , $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 465$ nm) as a function of externally added Mg^{2+} (0.05–300 μM).

Fig. 9. Plot of emission intensities of HISDAL (30 μM , $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 365$ nm, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 465$ nm) as a function of externally added Mg^{2+} (upto 10 μM).

Fig. 10. Changes in the absorbance of HISDAL (30 μM , aqueous-methanol, 1 : 9, v/v) upon gradual addition of Mg^{2+} (0–300 μM).

Fig. 11. Emission intensities of $[\text{HISDAL} + \text{Mg}^{2+}]$ system in presence of competing cations.

Fig. 12. Visual colour changes obtained upon addition of equimolar of various cations to the aqueous-methanol solution of HISDAL under UV light in the dark.

1597; $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ 1633, suggesting a shift of the band from the positions of free HISDAL.

Physical measurements :

FTIR spectra are recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer (Model no. IR Prestige 21). Absorption studies are carried out using a Shimadzu (Model no. 1800) UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Mass spectra are performed using a QTOF Micro YA 263 mass spectrometer in electron spray ionization (ESI) positive mode. ^1H NMR spectra in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ is recorded with a Bruker Avance 600 MHz using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. Fluorescence spectra are recorded with a Hitachi F-4500 fluorescence spectrometer. Measurements of pH are performed with a Systronics digital pH meter (Model 335).

General method of UV-Vis and fluorescence titration :

Path length of the cells used for absorption and emission studies is 1 cm. Stock solutions of HISDAL and Mg^{2+} are prepared in water/ CH_3OH (1/9, v/v). Working solutions of HISDAL and Mg^{2+} are prepared from their respective stock solutions. Fluorescence measurements are performed using 5 nm \times 5 nm slit width.

Job's plot from fluorescence experiments :

A series of solutions containing HISDAL and MgSO_4 are prepared such that the total concentration of Mg^{2+} and HISDAL remain constant (100 μM) in all the sets. The mole fraction (X) of HISDAL is varied from 0.1 to 0.8. The fluorescence intensity at 465 nm is plotted against the mole fraction of HISDAL.

Calculation of detection limit :

For the determination of detection limit, fluorescence titration of HISDAL with Mg^{2+} was carried out by the addition of aliquot of μM Mg^{2+} . The minimum concentra-

Fig. 13. Job's plot for determination of stoichiometry of the [HISDAL + Mg^{2+}] complex in aqueous-methanol (1 : 9, v/v) solution, λ_{ex} , 365 nm, λ_{em} , 465 nm.

tion of Mg^{2+} which result a sharp change in the fluorescence intensity multiplied with the concentration of HISDAL give the detection limit (DL)²¹.

$$DL = [HISDAL] \times [Mg^{2+}]; DL = (3.0 \times 10^{-5}) \times (0.05 \times 10^{-7}) = 0.05 \times 10^{-7} = 5.0 \times 10^{-9}$$

Calculation of quantum yield :

Fluorescence quantum yields (Φ) were estimated by integrating the area under the fluorescence curves using the equation,

$$\Phi_{\text{sample}} = \frac{OD_{\text{standard}} \times A_{\text{sample}}}{OD_{\text{sample}} \times A_{\text{standard}}} \times \Phi_{\text{standard}} \times \frac{\eta_{\text{sample}}^2}{\eta_{\text{standard}}^2}$$

where A is the area under the fluorescence spectral curve, OD is optical density of the compound at the respective excitation wavelength²² and η is the refractive indices of the solvents. Anthracene is used as quantum yield standard (quantum yield is 0.27 in ethanol) for measuring the

Fig. 14. QTOF-MS spectrum of [HISDAL + Mg^{2+}] complex in CH_3OH .

Fig. 15. Determination of association constant of HISDAL for Mg^{2+} in aqueous-methanol (1 : 9, v/v) solution, λ_{ex} , 365 nm, λ_{em} , 465 nm using fluorescence technique.

quantum yields of HISDAL and $[HISDAL + Mg^{2+}]$ systems for excitation wavelength of 365 nm²³.

Determination of binding constant :

The binding constant of HISDAL for Mg^{2+} is determined using a modified Benesi-Hildebrand equation²⁴ : $(F_{max} - F_{min}) / (F_x - F_{min}) = 1 + (1/K) (1/[C]^n)$ where F_{max} , F_{min} and F_x are emission intensity values for HISDAL in the presence of Mg^{2+} at saturation, in the absence of Mg^{2+} and at any intermediate Mg^{2+} concentration, respectively. A plot of $(F_{max} - F_0) / (F_x - F_0)$ vs $1/[C]$ (here $n = 1$) yields the binding constant value from the slope as $8.78 \times 10^4 M^{-1}$.

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Fig. 16. Comparison of FTIR spectra of HISDAL and $[HISDAL + Mg^{2+}]$ complex.

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